

In order to address causal credibility, the biological interactions of the human receptors and neural pathways are used as the blueprint for the choice of the input features as well as network architecture. A potential causal structure of the newly developed neuronal thermal sensation model (VANN, *Vote of Artificial Neural Network*) is shown in Figure 2. For the setup of the configuration of this feedforward network, the free software GNU Octave for the numerical solution of mathematical problems is used. For the activation of the hidden layer neurons the *sigmoid* function $1/(1 + e^{-z})$ and the output layer the *softmax* function $e^z / \sum_i e^{z_i}$ (for backpropagation their derivatives) are chosen. These functions are supposed to simulate the neuronal firing rates of thermoreceptors (with z as the weighted activation of the previous layer denoting the threshold mark).

Figure 2. Processing of thermal sensation (acc. [4]) of peripheral and central nervous system. [Left: own illustration; right: Adapted "Nervous system diagram," by Medium69 (wikimedia.org). CC BY-SA 4.0.]

Results and discussion

Through the integration of the physiological and sensation model into TRNSYS and its connection to a thermodynamic building model, which provides the environmental input data, two main objectives are pursued: First, the internal thermal quality of a building can be better and more reliably assessed throughout the design process of the building. Second, the thermal sensation votes produced by the VANN can provide the input for causal occupant behaviour models, such as the cognitive action model currently being developed at the University of Liechtenstein [5].

Conclusions

This approach is intended to put the human being and understanding of his or her needs and the associated interaction with the building into the centre of a building's design, which is an essential step for the development of reliable strategies to optimise the energy consumption. Further, the model code could also be used for smart building or even automotive applications.

References

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